

Exploring the Financial Implications of Seismic Events on Tall Pier Bridge Infrastructure

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ABSTRACT - This paper describes a methodology for the analysis and design of Reinforced Concrete (RC) tall bridge piers having different Solid Circular cross sections, which are typically used in deep valley bridge viaducts. Piers are usually considered tall when the shaft has a height excess of 30 m. Cost comparison has been carried out of tall pier road bridges varying 30m to 100m in height and also varying grade of concrete from M40, M50, M60 and M70. From this study one can easily adopt which combination of concrete and steel is to be proven more economical among all the combinations for the particular height. Various analysis has been performed for the R.C.C. Road Bridges with help of STAAD.Pro software. Kutch-Bhuj earthquake (2001) time-history data is used for the analysis. The main objective of the study is to develop cost-generating data which aids the students/consultant engineer to take the appropriate decision regarding tall pier bridges.

Keywords: High pier; Non-linear method; RC bridge; Seismic condition; Time-history analysis; 3D modelling.

I. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

The past two decade have seen unprecedented growth of the knowledge in the field of concrete bridges, development of new structural forms, and new methods of computer based analysis and design and development of high strength materials. The need for new rationalised methods for bridge structure in general, based on limit state approach, in line with international practices, has been felt for long time. Keeping view of this, the task of this study for concrete bridges is to establish a common procedure for design of bridges with consideration of earthquake effects in India based on the limit state method.

Mountain Bridge is generally consists of variable pier heights, so not only the geometry of the bridge will affect its earthquake response; the height and type of pier major factors affecting earthquake response. Under the force of earthquake, the combination of high pier and short pier made the force of bridge even more complicated.

An earthquake is a sudden, violent shaking of the ground (earth crust). Earthquake is the worst among the natural disasters. It is very important to design the structure after understanding the behaviour of the earthquake. The structural designer has several alternatives to choose from when defining a structural system that fit the architectural layout.

In these years, many bridges are being built in the northern and northeast of India at Himalaya region. Because of complex topography of bridge sit, many high piers bridges with different pier configurations in mountainous areas are used. The Northeast Frontier Railway's (NFR) construction organization has started constructing a bridge, which is slated to be the world's tallest after completion. This bridge near Noney in Manipur has a height of pillars rising up to 141 metres. This bridge is slated to become the tallest in the world from the point of view of pillar height surpassing the existing tallest of Mala-Rijeka viaduct on Belgrade-Bar railway line in Europe where the height of pillars is 139 meters. The another under-construction railway bridge is coming up on the Chenab river valley in Jammu-Kashmir, bridging a gorge of about 360 meters deep from the bed of the river to the rail level. It is considered as the highest railway bridge in the world.

II. SEISMIC EFFECTS ON TALL BRIDGE

For the severe damage of bridges in the past earthquakes, most designers have pay attention to the seismic design of high piers for mountain bridges. It is difficult to repair after the bridge damaged by the earthquake, because designers of domestic and foreign lack of the design experience about high piers under high-intensity earthquake. The damage of the major earthquake in the world, the damage of high piers bridge in mountain mainly focuses on the following, First, the damage of abutment, such as position of abutment changed, abutment settlement, wing-wall damaged and cracking, dislocation of construction joints as well as collision and damage of the main beam. (Figure-2). Second, the damage of piers and piles, such as piers and piles inclined, breaking and cracking, the steel yielded of lower part of concrete bridge pier, etc. The damage of main beams, falling of the beam is the most common, the reasons are the collapse of piers, damage of supports, collision of beams and large relative displacement between adjacent piers resulted in lacking of adequate beam

device. (Figure-3). Third, the damage of supports, such as supports inclined, cut, anchor bolt pull-out, roller supports rolling off, supports its own destruction, etc. (Figure-4).

Figure-1 Displacements and Rotation of Bridge

Figure-2 Damage of Abutment

Figure-3 Damages in Piers and Falling of Beams

Analysis of a structure, applying data over increment time steps as a function of:
 Acceleration
 Force
 Moment, or
 Displacement

Figure-4 Damages in Bearings

III. TIME HISTORY ANALYSIS

The closer the spacing of time steps, the more accurate the solution will be. Eigen values generated for the structure based on response to time history. Considered to be more realistic compared to response spectrum analysis. Most useful for very long or very tall structures (flexible structures). It is very time consuming method and generates (and requires) large quantities of data. The study showed that the high bridge pier may enter a state of serious non-linear elastic-plastic under a strong earthquake. At this point, the time history analysis method is more adaptive than the response spectrum method.

IV. METHOD OF STUDY

An R.C.C. road bridge having deck size of 100m x 16m is taken for the study. This bridge is considered under the seismic effect. In this case the Earthquake force is predominant than the wind pressure, hence the structure is analysed and designed for the Seismic Loading. Analysis using STAAD software, by taking different pier heights and different cross section diameters from which changes in parameters has been found and also cost comparison by varying different concrete grade. The following Table-1 guides regarding the different alternative schemes taken for carry out the study.

TABLE-1 BRIDGE DETAILS

Deck size of the Bridge	100m x 16m
Nos. of Span and its Length	4 nos. of span each 25m Long
Nos. of Lane and its Width	4 nos. of lane each 4m Wide
Height of Pier	30m, 50m, 70m, 80m, 90m and 100m
Pier Configuration	Solid Circular
Grade of Concrete	M40, M50, M60 and M70
Grade of Steel	Fe415 and Fe500

Following table shows the price list of various grade of concrete, various diameter of steel and shuttering cost.

TABLE-2 LIST OF VARIOUS COST

GRADE OF CONC.	CONC. PRICE	DIA. OF STEEL	STEEL PRICE
	Rs/m ³		Rs/kg
M40	5200		
M50	5700	25	42.5
M60	6100	32	42.5
M70	6600	40	44.0
SHUTTERING COST		1000 Rs/m ² above 30m height	
CONCRETING COST		150 Rs/m ³ every 10m height above 20m height	

V. MODELLING

The various Analysis performed for the R.C.C. Bridges considering seismic analysis method. The Bridge model as space frame with rigid joints. The fixity is treated as base. The superstructure and loads are remain same for all the analysis. The Time-history analysis is done by the software named STAAD.Pro. In this study, Kutch-Bhuj earthquake (2001) time-history data is used for nonlinear time-history analysis (Fig-5). Figure-6 shows the 3D view of STAAD model of bridge. Loadings and their combinations are applied as per IRC: 6-2014, as mention in fig 5-6.

Figure-5 Bhuj Earthquake Time-History

Figure-6 3D Rendered View of Bridge Model

TABLE-3 LOADS AND LOAD COMBINATIONS

Applied Loads	Multiplying Factor
Dead Load (Self Weight)	1.05
Live Load (Vehicle + Impact + Breaking)	0.20
Temperature Load	0.50
Seismic Load	+ or - 1.5

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cost comparison has been carried out for tall pier road bridges varying 30m to 100m in height and also varying grade of concrete from M40, M50, M60 and M70. From this study one can easily adopt which combination of concrete and steel is to be prove more economical among all the combinations for the particular height.

Selection criteria for the diameter of single solid pier for the particular height, by keeping maximum deflection at top of pier in the earthquake direction constant (i.e. 40-45 mm) for all the heights and diameter of double solid pier chosen by keeping i) L/D ratio same with central tie, ii) c/s area same with central tie and iii) c/s area same w/o tie.

Tabular form of Cost comparison result shown as shown in table 4

TABLE-4 RESULT TABLE

Discription	30 M				50 M				70 M				80 M				90 M				100 M			
	Single	Double			Single	Double			Single	Double			Single	Double			Single	Double			Single	Double		
	Solid	(Tie + L/D)	(Tie + Area)	w/o Tie	Solid	(Tie + L/D)	(Tie + Area)	w/o Tie	Solid	(Tie + L/D)	(Tie + Area)	w/o Tie	Solid	(Tie + L/D)	(Tie + Area)	w/o Tie	Solid	(Tie + L/D)	(Tie + Area)	w/o Tie	Solid	(Tie + L/D)	(Tie + Area)	w/o Tie
Pier Dia. M	1.8	0.9	1.25	1.27	2.8	1.2	1.9	1.95	3.3	1.7	2.3	2.3	3.55	1.8	2.5	2.5	3.75	1.9	2.6	2.65	3.85	2	2.7	2.75
Deflection mm	43	7	4.3	5.4	39	8.1	6.2	7	42	7.9	6.35	6.3	38	7.8	6	5	42	7.3	5.5	6	40	7.3	5.5	6
Total Area m ²	2.55	1.27	2.55	2.6	6.16	3.1	6.1	6	8.56	4.55	8.7	8.4	9.9	6.2	9.82	9.8	11	6.75	11.5	11.24	11.64	7.6	12	11.9
L/D Ratio	16.67	16.67	12	23.1	17.86	17.86	13.16	25	21.21	21.21	15.22	30.43	22.54	22.3	16	32	24	23.7	17.31	34	26	25	18.52	36.4
Total Opti. Cost of Pier per M	26150	25560	36080	31650	60125	50030	72930	62050	89970	68320	101100	106290	108610	75950	116130	136360	125785	85190	123330	168364	135365	101280	133860	216705
Grade of Conc.	M40	M50	M40	M50	M40	M40	M40	M40	M40	M40	M40	M40	M60	M40	M40	M40	M70	M40	M40	M50	M70	M40	M40	M70
Moment Mx	2505	165	550	625	4160	475	1310	1450	4230	620	1560	1565	4470	670	1750	1760	4680	705	1830	1855	4790	750	1920	1960
Moment Mz	3225	70	150	305	3235	140	290	565	3240	145	390	590	3240	155	400	610	3250	165	400	630	3290	170	400	640
Force Fy	11100	5200	5600	5650	15500	6920	8370	8630	20600	8750	11780	11650	24700	9820	14170	14050	32900	11050	16160	16500	35300	12450	19400	18270

As the height of the pier increases, % required steel increases and decreases with increasing Concrete grade. % required steel is higher for Double circular pier (Tie + Area) then the other type and very less for Double circular pier (Tie + L/D).

As per IRC: 21-2000, Clause 306.1 and 306.2, minimum 0.8% steel has to be provided.

% cost contribution of steel varies 16 to 50 % of total cost as compare to its % requirement only 0.8 to 3.1 %, from this we can say that, small variation in % steel can change the cost of construction very rapidly.

By keeping the grade of concrete same % cost contribution of steel increases with increasing pier height, because of increase in %steel requirement. As the grade of concrete increases, % cost contribution of steel decreases.

Graphical representations of cost comparison and its discussions are as follows in figure 7-10

Combine study of C.I. and optimum cost per meter for all types of pier shows that, Double (Tie + L/D) type pier proves most economical for all the heights and Double (w/o Tie) proves uneconomical then the others. Moment increases with increasing the pier height for all pier types.

As the diameter of pier increases moment increases and variation in the moment is not related with whether the Tie member provided or not, for Double pier having same c/s area with or without tie, moments are almost equal.

Variation in Transverse moment for each pier types shows in the chart, where x is height of pier between 30 to 100 m. Longitudinal moment decrease by providing central Tie member between two piers.

Value of longitudinal moment decrease by decreasing pier diameter for particular height.

For Single Solid pier moment decrease with increasing the height because higher diameter use and very less change in loading pattern.

For Double circular piers marginally increment in longitudinal moment are seen.

Variation in Longitudinal moment for each pier types shows in the chart, where x is height of pier between 30 to 100 m.

TABLE-5 FINAL COMMENTS

PIER TYPE	DISCUSSION
SINGLE SOLID	IT PROVES ECONOMICAL UP TO 30 M HT. ONLY FOR RC ROAD BRIDGES.
DOUBLE (TIE+L/D)	MOST ECONOMICAL TYPE OF PIER FORM AMONG ALL SELECTED TYPES FOR ALL THE HT.
DOUBLE (TIE+AREA)	20 TO 50 % COSTLY THEN THE DOUBLE (TIE + L/D) TYPE PIER, BUT HAVING LESS DEFLECTION AT TOP, DUE TO THIS IT IS MOST SUITABLE FOR RC RAIL BRIDGES.
DOUBLE (W/O TIE)	IT IS MOST UNECONOMICAL THEN THE OTHER TYPES OF PIER.

Figure-7 Combine study of the cost index

Figure-8 Combine study of the optimum cost per meter

Figure-9 Comparing Trans Moments at the base of pier

Figure-10 Comparing Long Moments at the base of pier

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